

Ollaberry,
Grimms Hill,
Great Missenden,
Bucks,
England,
27/11/71.

Mr. David Philips,
Regional Director,
The British Council,
Dubai,
P.O.B. 1636.

Dear Mr. Philips,

I have just returned to England from field work in Iran and Beatrice de Cardi handed me a copy of your letter of 20 September with the note from Kamal Hamza about finding a Museum Curator for Dubai. The job of starting a museum at Dubai would I must say appeal to me.

For the last four years I have been conducting research on Islamic and Sassanian settlement patterns and trade routes in Southern Iran and have excavated two sites near the Gulf. I have just received a Research Studentship (Junior Fellowship) from the Queen's College Oxford for the specific purposes of continuing my investigations on the Arab side of the Gulf and especially to examine the origins and history of the pearling industry. I did meet you briefly in January when I was in Dubai investigating the feasibility of this research. The curriculum vitae attached gives details of my formal qualifications, publications, and of the title of my doctoral thesis which I intend to submit after a few months. During this research I have had practical experience of the problems involved in map preparation, drafting, and photography. I have no formal background to Museum work but I have had close contact with several members of museum staffs and students of museum work, and am very ~~interested~~ attracted to the idea of putting across to the public my own interests by means of instructive museum display. Certainly when I visited Dubai I met a good deal of enthusiasm and eagerness to learn from people very much in need of the professional guidance I would enjoy providing.

I have a number of questions about the job which I would like to put: What is the geographical area in which the museum operates? Will it be the present Northern Trucial States, the whole U.A.E. or a smaller area? What is the organisation of the Museum collections at present in terms of

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finance and building? I am afraid that my arabic is very poor indeed. I would very much need and appreciate a chance for tuition. Would that be possible at Dubai? What would the curator's relationship be to the material at Jumeira? As presently displayed, despite the fine building, the objects must mean very little to a layman. Yet they could with the help of photographic material form the basis for a nice little exhibition of Dubai's trading position at a period long before any Europeans appeared in the Gulf, which would perhaps make rather an appropriate initial exhibition.

I agree with you very much about the need before it is too late to collect and arrange exhibits of recent ethnographic material. I would of course if I received the post wish to lay emphasis also on the pearling industry and on obtaining archaeological exhibits.

I am currently completing my thesis and am not in a position to take up the post immediately if it were offered to me, nor do I believe that going straight out to Dubai would meet the best interests of the museum. What I would suggest, if the Municipality is prepared to pay an air fare twice is that I visit Dubai fairly soon, perhaps in February when I could meet both you and, I hope your successor, or I could come earlier. A two or three week trip would enable me first to guide the direction of work your volunteers are taking, and second to examine the resources and needs of the museum. Then, on my return to England I would be in a position to plan the direction the museum should take, to consult with experts on its problems, to prepare photographic displays of historical and archive material, to research the local historical background to purchase equipment which may not be obtainable in Dubai. I would then be able to take up the job in the summer with all the preparation and equipment necessary.

I would be prepared to accept a contract for a year or less, although I hope in that time I could justify a renewal of the contract. I notice that a flat, transport, and secretarial and other services would be provided. I remember though, that life in Dubai did not seem cheap. We could perhaps discuss the salary if we agree on other points.

Best wishes in your own work in Dubai.

Yours sincerely

Andrew Williamson.

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